

Thermochromic Behaviour of Buffered Indicator Solutions. Part-IV. Thermodynamics of the Ionisation of *N*-(2-Acetamidol)iminoacetic Acid in Water and Aqueous Methanol

F. H. JUMEAN

Department of Chemistry, University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan

Manuscript received 4 September 1990, revised 22 January 1992, accepted 1 April 1992

The thermochromic method was used to obtain apparent thermodynamic parameters for the ionisation of *N*-(2-acetamidol)iminoacetic acid (ada) in water and in aqueous solutions containing 10, 20 and 30% (w/w) methanol. These were derived by analysis of the spectra of ada-neutral red solutions collected over a 50° temperature range. The free energy values were obtained potentiometrically. Transfer and medium effect terms for ada species were evaluated.

In an earlier communication¹, apparent ionisation parameters for the indicator neutral red in aqueous methanol were obtained with the aid of the thermochromic method^{2,3}. In that case, visible spectra of solutions containing sodium dihydrogen phosphate and neutral red were recorded over a 50°-range. These spectra exhibited remarkably high sensitivity to temperature. This behaviour makes it possible to couple neutral red with buffers whose p*K* values, for best accuracy, lie within ±1 p*K* units of that of the indicator. Thermochromic measurements are then expected to yield the requisite ionisation parameters.

Details of the thermochromic method have already been presented¹⁻³. For the buffer-indicator systems heretofore investigated, the ratio of the base to the acid forms of the indicator, *R*, has been fitted to the equation³,

$$\log R = a/T - b + cT \quad (1)$$

where *T* is the Kelvin temperature and *a*, *b* and *c* are constants obtained from regression analysis. The thermodynamic difference values are then calculated from the equations³,

$$\delta \Delta G' = \Delta G'_{\text{B}} - \Delta G'_{\text{I}} = 2.303 R (a - bT + cT^2) \quad (2)$$

$$\delta \Delta H' = \Delta H'_{\text{B}} - \Delta H'_{\text{I}} = 2.303 R (a - cT^2) \quad (3)$$

$$\delta \Delta S' = \Delta S'_{\text{B}} - \Delta S'_{\text{I}} = 2.303 R (b - 2cT) \quad (4)$$

$$\delta \Delta C'_P = \Delta C'_{\text{P,B}} - \Delta C'_{\text{P,I}} = -4.606 R cT \quad (5)$$

in which the subscripts B and I refer to buffer and indicator species. Ada, first synthesised by Good *et al.*⁴, belongs to the class of aliphatic cationic amines which are useful as buffers in the biological pH range. It has three p*K*'s, corresponding to the proton ionisations of H₃A⁺. The one of interest is p*K*_a, related to either of the possible equilibria,

At 20°, p*K*'s in water are 6.62 for ada⁴ and 6.77

for neutral red⁵, thus meeting the condition of close proximity of p*K* values.

Results and Discussion

For each buffer-indicator solution, a set consisting of at least 15 visible spectra was obtained in the temperature interval 2–55°. Furthermore, for each solvent composition, at least three such sets of repetitive scans were collected. In all cases, the maxima for the acid and base forms of the indicator were located at 528 and 454 nm, respectively, with an isosbestic point at 474 nm. The pH of all solutions was maintained at *ca.* 6.8 at 25°. The pH-readings in the mixed solvent were converted to the true (pH*) values using the equation, pH* = pH - δ, where δ is a small positive constant⁷. This correction was made because the pH meter is calibrated with aqueous solvent and thus its readings in non-aqueous media ought to allow for the liquid junction and medium effect terms, both of which are included in δ. Although the precise pH value has been shown³ not to directly influence the constants of equation (2), good measurement sensitivity requires the pH to be fairly close to the indicator's p*K*.

The absorbance values at 528 nm were observed to decrease with increasing temperature, with the exception of those in purely aqueous solutions, for which the absorbance vs temperature plot exhibited a minimum at 296.5 K. The overall magnitude of the thermochromic change, however, increased progressively on going from water to 30% methanol. This behaviour is reflected in increasing slopes of the log *R* vs 1/*T* plots (Fig. 1) as the methanol content is raised. The points are the experimental results and the solid curves are best fits to equation (1) as obtained from a computer regression program. Due to the apparently parabolic dependence of absorbance on temperature for data in pure water, it seemed that the results in this solvent might be better

described by an expression of the type,

$$\log R = \log R_m + b(T - T_m)^2 \quad (7)$$

where b is a constant and T_m the temperature at which R has its maximum value, R_m . Equation (7) may be readily derived in a manner analogous to that employed for the derivation of equation (1) on the assumption that the pK 's of both indicator and buffer follow the equation⁶,

$$pK = pK_m + b'(T - T_m)^2 \quad (8)$$

In order to determine the better fit, regression analysis was performed on data in water using equations (1) and (7) and the observed T_{max} value of 296.5 K. The results are depicted in Fig. 1(a), which shows the experimental points as well as the behaviour predicted by equations (1) and (7) (solid and dashed curves, respectively). It is apparent that equation (1) fairly represents the data throughout the temperature range investigated, whereas equation (7) is satisfactory for intermediate and higher ranges only. Accordingly, thermodynamic calculations were based on equation (1).

Fig. 1. Dependence of $\log R$ on $1/T$ for system ada-neutral red in water and in 10, 20 and 30% (w/w) methanol (a, b, c, d, and respectively). The solid curves are best fits to equation (1) and the points represent experimental values. The dashed curve in (a) is a plot of equation (7). For clarity, curves (b) and (d) are moved up and down 0.1 units, respectively, along the $\log R$ axis.

Table 1 summarises the results. The constants of equation (1) and the thermodynamic difference values as obtained from equations (2–5) are tabulated. The values of T_{max} , or $(1/T_{min})$, corresponding to the temperature at which $\log R$ vs $1/T$ plot has its minimum value, are also given. These are calculated from $T_{max} = (a/c)^{1/2}$ obtained from differentiation of equation (1). The value of 296.5 K in water is also observed directly since it lies within the experimental temperature range. The large drop in T_{max} with methanol

addition is largely due to the $\delta\Delta C'_p$ terms, which become progressively less negative. This explains the decline in the curvature of the $\log R$ vs $1/T$ plots with methanol addition.

TABLE 1—CONSTANTS a , b AND c OF EQUATION (1) AND APPARENT THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE IONISATION OF THE INDICATOR NEUTRAL RED (I) AND THE BUFFER ADA (B) AT 298.15 K

	Methanol % (w/w)			
	0	10	20	30
a	5116	1971	943.1	-1.00
b	33.91	14.68	9.22	3.18
c	0.058	0.028	0.021	0.011
$\Delta(\Delta G') \pm 0.10$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	3.43	1.59	1.02	1.04
$\Delta(\Delta H') \pm 0.08$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-1.10	-9.92	-17.52	-19.95
$\Delta(\Delta S') \pm 2$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-15.2	-38.6	-62.2	-68.1
$\Delta(\Delta C'_p) \pm 8$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-664	-320	-239	-129
T_{max} (K)	296.5	265.3	212.4	—
$\Delta H'_I$ (kJ mol ⁻¹) ^a	17.70	24.08	30.72	34.40
$\Delta S'_I$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹) ^a	-79.4	-57.9	-40.1	-32.1
$\Delta C'_{p,I}$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹) ^a	345	246	175	-103
pK'_B	6.811	6.756	6.838	6.892
$\Delta G'_B \pm 0.03$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	38.88	38.57	39.04	39.34
$\Delta H'_B \pm 0.14$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	16.60	14.16	13.20	15.15
$\Delta S'_B \pm 3$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-94.6	-96.5	-112	-100
$\Delta C'_{p,B} \pm 14$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-319	-74	-64	-232

^aRef. 1.

The apparent thermodynamic ionisation values for ada may now be obtained from equations (2–5) making use of the known values for neutral red¹. Here, a potential source of error may become highly significant when the ionisation constants for buffer and indicator are very close, as in the present system. In such cases, $\delta\Delta G'$ is necessarily small and hence calculation of $\Delta G'_B$ from $\delta\Delta G'$ and $\Delta G'_I$ may lead to large errors, since the outcome is a small difference between two large numbers. It was thus deemed necessary to obtain $\Delta G'_B$ values directly. This was done by potentiometric titrations under nitrogen atmosphere in a cell thermostated at 298.15 K, with solution and titrant having identical solvent compositions. Analysis of the titration curves yielded the pK'_B values listed in Table 1. The existence of a minimum in 10% methanol is consistent with the isoelectric ionisation of equation (6b) rather than (6a) which, due to charge creation, becomes highly unfavourable as the dielectric constant of the medium is lowered by methanol addition. The initial drop in pK'_B reflects the increased basicity of the medium as methanol is added⁷. The subsequent increase occurs when changes in the electrostatic component of pK become dominant with further methanol addition. The small dependence of pK'_B on solvent suggests that the opposing effects attributed to the medium's basicity and dielectric constant, have comparable magnitudes in the solvent range investigated.

Table 1 lists thermochromic values for $\Delta H'_B$, $\Delta S'_B$ and $\Delta C'_{p,B}$ and potentiometric ones for $\Delta G'_B$. The thermochromic result of 16.60 kJ mol⁻¹ for $\Delta H'_B$ in water is reasonably close to the potentiometric one of 17.50 kJ mol⁻¹,

calculated from data by Good *et al.*⁴. It is noteworthy that a minimum in $\Delta H'_B$ is observed in 20% methanol, caused by the interplay of the positive free energy and the negative entropy terms. Here, it may be noted that whereas the solvent dependence of $\Delta G'_B$ may be explained in terms of electrostatic and non-electrostatic terms, the behaviour of $\Delta H'_B$ is much more complex, usually involving structural and steric factors which are often difficult to assess⁸. The $\Delta S'_B$ values are all negative but their dependence on solvent is small, varying from -94.6 to $-100 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. These are *ca.* $25-32 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ less negative than those for proton dissociations of mononegative ions and are closer to the values for neutral molecules⁹. This adds support to the dissociation occurring from HA^{-+} rather than HA^- . Clearly, ionisation of HA is accompanied by more ordering than that of HA^{-+} , due to increased orientation of solvent molecules around the newly created charges. The large negative $\Delta C'_{p,B}$ values in water and 30% methanol (-319 and $-232 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively), indicate that the ionisation is significantly less endothermic at higher temperatures. In the water case, thermal effects may loosen tightly bound water molecules surrounding the ion, thereby allowing more H-bonding with the dissociated ions. In 30% methanol, interpretation of $\Delta C'_{p,B}$ is difficult, though there may be a connection to the breakdown of water structure in this relatively methanol-rich solvent. Such a breakdown is supported by its unusually high basicity, as seen from the value of $-6.80 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ (Table 2) for the free energy of proton transfer from water to this medium⁸.

TABLE 2—APPARENT THERMODYNAMIC VALUES AT 298.15 K, FOR THE TRANSFER OF ADA SPECIES FROM WATER TO AQUEOUS METHANOL

	Methanol % (w/w)		
	10	20	30
$\Delta H'_t$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-2.44	-3.40	-1.45
$\Delta S'_t$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-1.9	-7.4	-5.4
$\Delta C'_{p,t}$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	246	256	87
$\Delta G'_t$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-0.31	0.16	0.46
ΔG_t (H ⁺) (kJ mol ⁻¹) ^a	-2.09	-3.81	-6.80 ^b
$\log (m\gamma_A^-/m\gamma_{\text{HA}^{-+}})$	0.31	0.69	0.08

^aRef. 8. ^bInterpolated value.

Table 2 lists the apparent thermodynamic values of transfer from water to the mixed solvent at 298.15 K. The free energy of transfer of species *i* is related to the medium effect, $m\gamma_i$, by the equation,

$$\Delta G'_t = \Delta G^\circ_s - \Delta G^\circ_w = 2.303 \log m\gamma_i \quad (9)$$

Since the tabulated $\Delta G'_t$ values refer to the transfer of one mole each of HA^{-+} , A^- , and H^+ from water (w) to the mixed solvent(s), it may be readily shown that

$$\Delta G'_t = 2.303 \log (m\gamma_{\text{H}^+} m\gamma_{\text{A}^-}/m\gamma_{\text{HA}^{-+}}) \quad (10)$$

Values for proton transfer from water to aqueous

methanol⁹ ($\Delta G'(\text{H}^+)$), are also listed. The medium effect term for ada species, $\log (m\gamma_{\text{A}^-}/m\gamma_{\text{HA}^{-+}})$, may thus be easily calculated using equations (9) and (10) and the transfer free energies of Table 2. Values for this term, at 298.15 K, are 0.31, 0.69 and 1.27 for transfer to 10, 20 and 30% methanol, respectively. The regular increase in this term indicates that transfer of the buffer species becomes energetically less favourable as the solvent is enriched with methanol. This in turn suggests that the decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium exerts more influence on the behaviour of the buffer species than the electrostatic factor. However, for the molecule as a whole, this effect is offset by $\Delta G'(\text{H}_+)$, which becomes progressively more negative with methanol addition.

Experimental

All chemicals were of reagent grade and used as such. Prior to use, ada was dried under reduced pressure for ~24 h. Spectral and pH measurements were conducted in the manner previously described¹. Temperatures were measured within 0.02° using a RS 151-192 thermocouple. Potentiometric titrations were performed under nitrogen, using *ca.* 0.1 mol dm^{-3} carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solutions. The *R* terms were calculated from the absorbance at 528 nm, the wavelength maximum for the acid form. At this wavelength the ratio of the absorbance of the acid to the base forms is fairly high, varying from 5.61 in water to 6.40 in 30% (w/w) methanol¹. The ionic strength was maintained at $0.050 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ by addition of NaCl. Indicator concentrations were varied in the vicinity of $10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to the University of Jordan for support and to Miss A. Arnout for performing the measurements.

References

1. F. H. JUMEAN and M. I. QADERI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 541.
2. F. H. JUMEAN, M. I. KHAMIS and G. N. SALAITA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 995.
3. F. H. JUMEAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 967.
4. N. E. GOOD, G. D. WINGET, W. WINTER, T. N. CONNOLLY, S. IZAWA and R. M. M. SINGH, *Biochemistry*, 1966, 5, 467.
5. F. H. JUMEAN, unpublished results.
6. R. G. BATES and R. A. ROBINSON in "Chemical Physics of Ionic Solutions", eds. B. E. CONWAY and R. G. BARRADAS, Wiley, New York, 1966, pp. 211-235.
7. H. S. HARNED and N. D. EMBREE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1050.
8. D. FEAKINS in "Physicochemical Processes in Mixed Aqueous Solvents", ed. F. FRANKS, Elsevier, New York, 1967, pp. 71-90.
9. J. J. CHRISTENSEN and R. M. IZATT, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 56, 1030.